

THE APPLICATION OF GENDER IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES.

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Abstract: *This article provides with the notions about the application of gender in Uzbek and English languages. In addition, the author provides examples in both languages.*

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In English, grammatical gender is a property of only nouns and pronouns. It is one of the simplest parts of English grammar for the concept is clear and consistent. This is because gender in English is based on natural gender than grammar. It is not so in many other languages, where the concept of grammatical gender is based on morphology and may apply not only to nouns and pronouns but also to other parts of speech such as adjectives and verbs. If English had grammatical gender then nouns, pronouns, even other parts of speech would have belonged to different gender groups depending upon their word-endings and even these would have had exceptions!

Look at these sentences...He gets upset. She remains calm. The lions stays with the cubs. The lion goes out to hunt. The man is an actor. The woman is an actress.

The pronoun he and the nouns lion, man, actor refer to male persons or animals. They belong to one class of gender. The pronoun she and the nouns lioness, woman, and actress refer to female persons or animals. Hence these belong to another class of gender. English divides nouns and pronouns into four genders in this way:

Masculine: All males (and only males) are said to belong to the masculine gender. (examples: boy, man, landlord, god, tiger, horse, rooster, stag, he)

Feminine: All females (and only females) belong to this gender category. (examples: girl, woman, goddess, landlady, tigress, mare, hen, doe, hind, she)

Common: Nouns and pronouns that belong to this gender are either male or female, but we are not concerned about it. (examples: teacher, child, worker, baby, infant, human being, person)

Neuter: All nouns and pronouns to which maleness or femaleness doesn't apply belong to this gender category. (Material things: stone, table, gold, book; all abstract nouns: childhood, independence, intelligence, chairmanship)

Nowadays some words in the Masculine Gender are used as Common Gender. Everybody doesn't do it, but if you follow this trend, you will be considered modern!

Actor - Used for both male and female—traditionally, actor and actress; poet for both poet and poetess. The purpose is to avoid gender bias about which people are very conscious today; governor - for both male and female. This is perhaps because the woman ruler of a province would not like the word 'governess' to be used for her lest people misunderstand that she is someone employed in a rich family to teach its children; priest - for both male and female.

Nowadays the linguistic realization of gender differences is one of the burning matters in social spheres, being at the same time the issue of constant misunderstandings. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to view the present-day status of the grammatical category of gender in Modern English as a result of language historical development as well as due to the pragmatic distinguishing of certain gender forms in different communicative situations. As is known, English gender is realized as masculine, feminine and neuter forms in order to explain the relations between the animate noun and its external referent. In different languages including English there are two basic types of gender systems: strict semantic system, or semantic gender, where the meaning of the noun determines its gender, and formal system, or grammatical gender, when the noun assignments depend on formal criteria - either word-structure or sound-structure.

The pronominal gender is greatly influenced by extralinguistic factors, such as context, time conditions and the speaker. Gender in the language reflects the social constructions of gender learned, maintained and perpetuated by speakers. Social constructions of gender represent combinations of features inherent in reality and of society's attitudes toward those features. There is no clear correlation of gender with sex: the choice of the pronoun that is used to denote the certain gender form depends not on characteristics of the noun or of its referent, but depends instead entirely on speaker-dependent factors, which are variable and unpredictable.

Therefore, the forms of gender indication are lexico-semantic (change of words: man -woman, bull-cow) and morphological (inflections: host - hostess, hero -heroine; addition of a word: male cat - female cat).

1. Instead of issuing stock certificates for each individual (common) share issued to a shareholder, a stock company can issue a single document (neuter) representing the aggregate number of shares owned by the individual shareholder.

2. It is hoped that the improved geopolitical situation (neuter), advantageous financial conditions (neuter), flexible macroeconomic policy (neuter), structural reforms (neuter) will condition (neuter) faster EU development (neuter) in the nearest years (neuter).

3. Local authorities (common) may also collect revenue (neuter) from a number of local taxes (neuter), such as advertisement tax (neuter), community development tax (neuter), hotel tax (neuter), parking tax (neuter), recreation tax (neuter), and other taxes (neuter).

4. Moreover, the values (neuter) of the acquired companies' (neuter) liabilities (neuter) and contingent liabilities (neuter) which had not been disclosed in the financial statements (neuter) of the companies (neuter) or were disclosed in lower amounts (neuter) was also increased as a result (neuter) of the valuation (neuter).

The stated above proves that the category of gender in Modern English is realized as semantic category, represented by means of lexico-semantic and morphological gender forms as well as pronouns used according to extralinguistic factors. The typological category of gender consists of the notions of natural (biological sex and the grammatical formal gender. The connection of this category with the natural sex is in the animals and birds. It is displayed by the nouns and pronouns in English. Most of the Uzbek grammar books do not contain any information about the category of gender of Uzbek nouns, because the authors consider Uzbek nouns not to have this category at all.

In accordance with their lexical meanings the nouns of the comparing nouns may be classed as belonging to the masculine, feminine and neuter genders. Names of male beings are usually masculine (man, husband, boy, son, nephew, bull, ox, cock, stallion – ота, уғил, эркак, ҳукиз, буқа, новвос, қучқор, хуроз, айғир) and names of female beings are feminine (woman, lady, girl, daughter, wife, niece, cow heifer(ғунажин), hen, mare аюол, хоним, қиз(бола), қиз (фарзанд), хотин, сигир) All other nouns are said to be neuter gender (pencil, flower, rain, bird, sky-қалам, гул, уомғир, парранда, қуш, осмон). Gender finds its formal expression in the replacement of nouns by the personal pronouns in the mind person singular, i.e., she, it. However, there some nouns in English which may be treated as either makes or females: friend, cousin, doctor, neighbor, worker, etc. The same can be said about the Uzbek terms of kinship: жиян, қариндош, холавачча, куда, қушни, табиб, ишчи. They are said to be of common (neuter) gender. When there is no need to make distinction of sex the masculine pronoun is used for these nouns.

There are three ways of expressing the category of gender in the comparing languages: morphological, syntactical and lexical. Morphological way of expressing the category of gender is realized by adding suffixes of gender to the stem of the word. English has the only suffix – ess which is used to denote feminine gender: host-ess, lion-ess, and tigr-ess. Feminine gender in Uzbek may often be expressed by means of the suffix- a which is supposed to be of Arabic origin: – раис а, вазир а, шоир а, муаллим а, котиб а. In order denote the gender syntactic way is also possible. In this case different kinds of combinations of words are formed in which adjunct word (modifier) usually denotes the sex of the head word. e.g.: man servant – қарол, amid servant оксоч, boyfriend-ўғил бола уртоқ, girlfriend-қиз бола ўртоқ, tom cat еркак мушук, tabby cat урғочи мушук, he-wolf еркак бўри, she wolf урғочи бўри, he goat така, she goat она ечки, etc. As is seen from these examples English gender denoted

by a syntactic combination (man servant she goat can be expressed in Uzbek both by syntactically and lexically, (қарол, она ечки).

In most cases gender can be expressed lexically by the stem of the noun only. e.g.: father ота, uncle амаки, niece – (қиз) жиян, sister-in-law келин.

Names of people can also denote the gender of the person who owns this name: Arthur, Christopher, John – Аҳмаджон, Баҳодир, Шаҳобиддин denoting male being and Mary, Christine, Nelly, – Сайера, Мехринисо, Гулоим.

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